

H2020-FNR-2020-2 Project no. 101000560

Rapid discovery and development of enzymes for novel and greener consumer products

Research and Innovation Action (RIA)

Start date: 01-06-2021

Duration: 4 years

D6.3 – Mid-term set of IP potential and FTO options for the consortium.

Work Package N°:	6
Deliverable N°:	6.5
Lead Beneficiary:	SUSMOM
Other participants:	
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RADICALZ combines research lines in an interdisciplinary approach, with the potential of generating innovation and knowledge that may be susceptible to be protected through patents and exploited commercially. Different chemicals targeting several markets (e.g. surfactants, nutraceuticals, antioxidants, food additives, sweeteners, etc.) are considered as final products. To anticipate the actions and research lines that can be worth protecting, an in-depth analysis of the state-of-the-art of each sub-topic was conducted (D6.1, M6). On that basis, the best innovation and IP strategies could be established, and recommendations were drawn timely. D6.5 (M24) provides an update of the patenting activities and innovation actions that have been reached at RADICALZ (period M1-M24). The project is proceeding successfully in the identification of novel enzymes (and variants thereof) that can tackle the production of compounds with high market potential. Two main aspects can be highlighted at this point:

- A European patent application has been filed (March 2023) by several RADICALZ partners, focusing on an enzymatic method to deliver bio-based amides in aqueous media. The invention focuses on novel enzyme variants combined with particular processing conditions. The obtained compounds occur in plants, and display properties that can be applied in pharmaceutical and food industries, provided that efficient synthetic procedures are established.
- In addition to that patent application, as of M24 (D6.5) several research lines are investigated within RADICALZ, with promising options to be secured over IP as well. Examples include the generation of novel nutraceuticals, food derivatives, surfactants, thickeners, or processes to clean industrial effluents. In all cases the primary target will be the generation of IP. Should this not be (strategically) relevant, Freedom-To-Operate (FTO) conditions will be assessed.

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